

Original Research Article

Teacher's Performance Improvement through Strengthening Decision Making, Learning Organizations and Self-Efficacy

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Abstract

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This study aims to find ways and strategies to improve teacher's performance by identifying the strength of the relationship between decision-making variables and teacher's performance, the strength of the relationship between learning organizations and teacher's performance, the strength of the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher's performance, both individually and collectively. This type of research is a quantitative research with correlational analysis and SITOREM analysis. The population in this study were all ASN teachers who served at State Islamic Junior High School in East Jakarta, amounting to 510 people. The research sample was taken using the Proportional Random Sampling technique with a size using the Slovin formula of 225 teachers. This means that teacher's performance can be improved through strengthening decision-making, learning organization, and self-efficacy both individually and together. The results of the analysis show that indicators of teacher's performance, decision making, learning organization, and self-efficacy that have been well maintained or developed, while those that are not good need to be corrected immediately.

Keywords: Decision Making, Learning Organization, Self-Efficacy, Teacher Performance

INTRODUCTION

One of the benchmarks for the progress of a country is the quality of education. The more developed a country, the better the quality of education. To produce a good national education, teachers who are professional and have good performance are needed. Teacher professionalism is closely related to the ability to realize or actualize the competencies required for every teacher. Meanwhile, competence is a specification of the knowledge, skills and attitudes that a person has and its application in work in accordance with the performance standards required by the field (Dirjen Dikdasmen, 2004). Competence is manifested in the form of mastery of knowledge, skills and professional attitudes in carrying out their duties. The position of the teacher is very strategic where the quality of education is largely determined by the quality of the work of the teacher. Teachers who have good performance in implementing learning will make a major contribution to the realization of the quality of education in an educational institution.

Good teacher performance is shown by the behavior of teachers in carrying out their duties professionally and in mastering the competencies that are the demands of their duties. 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards, it is stated that the competencies that must be possessed by teachers include pedagogic competence, social competence, professional competence, and personality competence. Furthermore, in Law number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, it has been stated that teachers as educators are professionals in charge of planning and implementing the learning process, assessing learning outcomes, conducting guidance and training, as well as conducting research and community service.

Teachers should show their best performance such as planning and preparing for teaching well, delivering the material to be taught to students properly, applying teaching methods and strategies appropriately, providing comprehensive guidance to students, managing classes

effectively, and conducting continuous assessment of student learning outcomes. Besides, the teacher's task is not only to teach students, but also to educate students to become physically and spiritually intelligent individuals. This is in order to realize the functions and objectives of national education, namely developing capabilities and shaping the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of educating the nation's life, aiming at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen. Professional teachers certainly have high performance in order to produce disciplined performance, achievement, loyalty, and responsibility for their professional duties. Teachers can improve their performance by doing positive things in carrying out their duties as a teacher such as teaching according to their workload, always being on time, never leaving the task of teaching, working well with fellow teachers, being honest, and so on. These positive things can influence educators to always develop their best potential in order to create a school that can produce students who excel in every field, both academic and non-academic. The existence of the teacher as the main implementer in the implementation of education makes a major contribution to the success of the implementation of education in educational institutions.

There are serious problems with teacher performance. Teachers who should have mastered correctly about teaching planning for their students have not been able to realize the results of good instructional design. A good teaching plan is of course oriented to the needs of students adjusted to the level of student development, adjusted to the background of students and oriented to students, student-centered so that learning implementation will be created that attracts active participation from students and is effective in achieving learning objectives.

Based on an initial survey through a questionnaire conducted on 60 teachers at MTsN in East Jakarta, it can be seen that:

1. There are 50% of teachers who have not optimally made planning and preparation for teaching well, this can be seen from the learning tools owned by the teacher are not in sync with the available time, and learning planning has not been linked to everyday life.
2. There are 51% of teachers who are less than optimal in delivering the material that will be taught to students properly, this can be seen from the lack of books and learning resources used.
3. There are 55% who are less than optimal in mastering teaching methods and strategies, it can be seen from the lack of variation in the use of methods and strategies as well as the media used in teaching and learning activities.

4. In the aspect of classroom management, there are 54% of teachers who are not optimal in classroom management, this can be seen from the lack of teacher mobility in class and the lack of guidance to students as a whole.

5. There are 50% of teachers who have not optimally assessed and evaluated well, this can be seen from the lack of analyzing the results of the test, the lack of remedial and enrichment for students and the lack of comprehensive assessment of both aspects of skills and attitudes

The low performance of teachers is also known from the data on the results of the teacher competency test conducted by the ministry of education and culture by referring to the official source of the Regional Education Balance (NPD) of the Ministry of Education and Culture, which states that the average result of UKG DKI Jakarta in 2015 was 62.58. And specifically for the East Jakarta City area, the UKG score at the junior high school level is 63.25. Furthermore, the UKG value for 2019 in DKI Jakarta has decreased with an average value of 54. Based on the preliminary survey data and the results of the teacher competency test above, it can be explained that the performance of MTs N teachers in East Jakarta City is still low. Therefore, it is necessary to improve teacher performance to a better stage. However, improving teacher performance takes time because it is related to various factors that influence it. The influencing factors include decision making, learning organization and self efficacy.

Decision making is one of the important factors for a school principal in carrying out the leadership function. The right decision making by the principal will have a positive impact on teachers performance. Principals not only provide direction and supervision to teachers, but are also required to be able to make the right decisions and communicate important matters in order to create a conducive and dynamic work atmosphere. Such an atmosphere in turn can spur increased performance. Decision making by school principals certainly affects teacher performance.

Self-efficacy or self-efficacy is related to a person's belief that he or she is able to perform the assigned task. Organization members who have high self-efficacy are confident of their success and will be more motivated to improve their skills so that it has a significant impact on improving their performance. On the other hand, low self-efficacy makes members of the organization hesitate to develop their competencies, reduces their participation in groups, thereby inhibiting members' contributions to innovation activities and new things in their work. The results of research by Hani Ratnasari and Nancy Yusnita at JIMFE (Scientific Journal of Management, Faculty of Economics) Vol. 4 No. 1, June 2018, p. 51-66 entitled Analysis of the Relationship of Self-Efficacy with Employee Performance at PT Metraplasa shows that the

self-efficacy variable has a significant relationship to employee performance, the correlation between the self-efficacy variable and employee performance shows a value of 0.573. The value of the coefficient of determination shows a percentage of 28.8% where the results show that the contribution of the self-efficacy variable to the employee performance variable is 28.8%. Thus there is a relationship between self-efficacy (X) and employee performance (Y) at PT Metraplas.

Based on the factors above, in an effort to improve teacher performance it is necessary to realize through strengthening the decision making of school principals in learning organizations and also strengthening teacher self-efficacy. Therefore, research on teacher performance, decision making of school leadership, learning organization and teacher self-efficacy is needed to provide guidance and reference for interested parties in maintaining and improving organizational performance to achieve the educational goals that have been set effectively and efficiently.

Based on the background of the research that has been described previously, this study aims to find ways and strategies to improve teacher performance which are used as input and recommendations to related parties to realize quality national education.

The method used is to identify the strength of the relationship between research variables, namely the identification of:

1. The strength of the relationship between decision making and teacher performance.
2. The strength of the relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance.
3. The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance.
4. The strength of the relationship between decision making and learning organization together with teacher performance.
5. The strength of the relationship between decision-making and self-efficacy together with teacher performance.
6. Strength of the relationship between learning organization and self-efficacy together with teacher performance
7. The strength of the relationship between decision making, learning organization and self-efficacy together with teacher performance.

METHOD

This research was conducted in 18 Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri (MTsN) located in East Jakarta City. The time of this research was carried out from February 2020 to July 2021.

This research uses a combination research method between Correlational Research and SITOREM Analysis . Correlational Research and SITOREM Analysis is a

combination research method that combines correlational research methods whose results are strengthened by using SITOREM analysis. Through SITOREM Analysis, the results of correlational research are analyzed in more detail on the indicators of the research variables, so as to find indicators that need to be improved and maintained or developed.

The Constellation of Relationships Between Research Variables can be described as follows:

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Figure 1. Constellation of relationships between research variables

Information:

X1 : Decision Making

X2 : Learning Organization

X3 : Self Efficacy

Y : Teacher Performance

(epsilon): Other related variables

The population in this study were teachers of ASN Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri (MTsN) in the East Jakarta City Region with a total of 510 teachers. The sample in this study was obtained using the Proportional Random Sampling technique, which is proportional random sampling. while to determine the number of samples from the population, the Slovin formula is used at a margin of error of 5%; so that the minimum number of samples set is 225 ASN teachers.

RESULT

Hypothesis Testing

Based on the calculation of each variable, a summary table of the results of the overall significant test calculation can be made as follows: Tables 1-3

Table 1. Resume of the Calculation Results of the Correlation Significance Test for Each Hypothesis

Correlation	Regression	Significant			Conclusion
		F _{value}	F _{table} α= 0,05	F _{table} α=0,01	
Y-X1	$\hat{Y} = 93,54 + 0,313 X_1$	8,04	3,88	6,75	Very Significant
Y-X2	$\hat{Y} = 101,18 + 0,257X_2$	22,78	3,88	6,75	Very Significant
Y-X3	$\hat{Y} = 86,757 + 0,373 X_3$	28,90	3,88	6,75	Very Significant
Y-X1 X2	$\hat{Y} = 70,840 + 0,271 X_1 + 0,219 X_2$	44,28	3,04	4,70	Very Significant
Y-X1 X3	$\hat{Y} = 65,23 + 0,24 X_1 + 0,30 X_3$	45,00	3,04	4,70	Very Significant
Y-X2 X3	$\hat{Y} = 62,97 + 0,223 X_2 + 0,334 X_3$	50,08	3,04	4,70	Very Significant
Y-X1 X2 X3	$\hat{Y} = 62,97 + 0,223 X_2 + 0,334 X_3$	16,96	3,04	4,07	Very Significant

Table 2. Resume of Regression Equation Linearity Test Calculation Results

Correlation	Regression	Linierity			Conclusion
		F _{value}	F _{table} α= 0,05	F _{table} α=0,01	
Y-X1	$\hat{Y} = 93,54 + 0,313 X_1$	-4,278	1,53	1,85	Linier
Y-X2	$\hat{Y} = 101,18 + 0,257X_2$	-3,665	1,50	1,79	Linier
Y-X3	$\hat{Y} = 86,757 + 0,373 X_3$	-4,331	1,53	1,85	Linier

Tabel 3. Resume Calculation Result of Correlation Coefficient Test and Hypothesis Test

Correlation	Coeficient	T _{value}	t _{table}		Conclusion
			α=0,05	α=0,01	
r _{y1}	0,412	10,616	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected, H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between decision making and teacher performance
r _{y2}	0,397	9,330	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance
r _{y3}	0,441	7,341	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance
r _{y1.2}	0,386	6,253	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between decision making and learning organizations with teacher performance
r _{y1.3}	0,563	10,181	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between decision making and self-efficacy with teacher performance
r _{y2.3}	0,408	6,685	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between learning organizations and self-efficacy with teacher performance
r _{y1.2.3}	0,863	215,45	1,97	2,60	H0 is rejected H1 is accepted, there is a positive relationship between decision making, learning organization, and self-efficacy with teacher performance

DISCUSION

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is proven that the seven hypotheses proposed can be accepted significantly. Overall, this study shows that there is a positive relationship between: 1) Principal decision-making and teacher performance, 2) Learning

organization and teacher performance, 3) Self-efficacy and teacher performance, 4) Principal decision-making and learning organizations together with teacher performance, 5) Principal decision-making and self-efficacy together with teacher performance, 6) Learning organization and self-efficacy together with teacher performance, 7) Principal decision-making, learning

organization, and self-efficacy together -same as teacher performance. The functional relationship formed between the independent variable and the dependent variable shows that teacher performance is the result of the principal's decision-making variables, learning organizations, and self-efficacy. The description of these seven hypotheses is explained as follows:

The Relationship Between Decision Making and Teacher Performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing the functional relationship between principal decision making and teacher performance is shown by the regression equation $= 93.539 + 0.313 X_1$, with $F_{count} = 8.038 > F_{table} (0.05) = 3.88$ and $F_{table} (0.01) = 6,75$ which means that the significance of the regression is very significant. The functional relationship is linear as evidenced by linearity test with a value of $F_{count} = -4.278 < F_{table} (0.05) = 1.53$ and $F_{table} (0.01) = 1.85$, which means that it is not significant or the regression is linear, it can be interpreted if the principal's decision making is increased by one unit, the teacher's performance is predicted to increase by 0.313 units with a constant of 93.539. This means that every increase in the principal's decision-making score will improve teacher performance, school principal's decision-making makes a positive contribution to improving teacher performance. The value of the correlation coefficient $r_{y1} = 0.412$ with a coefficient of determination $R_{y1} = 0.1697$. This means that 16.97% of teacher performance is the result of the work of the principal's decision-making variable, while 83.03% is contributed by other variables that have a relationship with improving teacher performance. $\beta_2 = 0.283$ and controlling for the self-efficacy variable is $r_{y1.3} = 0.245$. From the two partial correlation tests, it can be concluded that the relationship between the principal's decision-making and teacher performance is very significant at the level of $= 0.05 (1.97)$ and $= 0.01 (2.60)$, with controlling for learning organization variables and efficacy. self. In other words, the relationship between the principal's decision-making and teacher performance is not significantly influenced by the learning organization variable and the self-efficacy variable.

From the research results obtained, it can be seen that decision making by the principal is a management activity that must be carried out by a leader in solving organizational problems so that the organizational goals that have been determined can be realized. Decisions are the result of solving problems they face decisively. Decisions are also the result of a thought process in the form of selecting one of several alternatives that can be used to solve the problems they face. Thus the decision is the result of solving the problem he faces firmly. It has to do with the answers to the questions of what to do. In other words, decision making is a process of selecting

the best alternative from several alternatives systematically to be followed up (used) as a way of solving problems. Appropriate and firm decision making can increase teacher confidence in the principal, so that it will have an impact on increasing teacher performance.

This is in line with the theory put forward by Triono (2017, p; 2) that decision making is a series of mental processes that a person does in determining a way out for the problems he faces. Decision making in a problem is a solution to the problems it faces, thus decision making is the last action taken by managers or leaders in an organization. In the decision-making process there are usually several choices that must be determined which one is best for achieving organizational goals, and usually this decision-making is based on certain criteria. Decision making is one of the important factors for a school principal in carrying out the leadership function. The right decision making by the principal will have a positive impact on teacher performance. Principals not only provide direction and supervision to teachers, but are also required to be able to make the right decisions and communicate important matters in order to create a conducive and dynamic work atmosphere. Such an atmosphere in turn can spur increased performance. Decision making by school principals certainly affects teacher performance. This is in line with research conducted by Muh. Nasrullah, et.al. in the *Journal of Administrare: Journal of Scientific Thought and Office Administration Education* Vol. 4, No. 2, July - December 2017, with the research title *The Effect of Principal Decision Making on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 1 Makassar*. The results showed that there was a positive influence between the principal's decision making and teacher performance with the regression equation; $Y = a + bX$, $Y = 24,409 + 0.656 X$. While the calculation of the product moment correlation of the principal's decision-making variable (variable X) with teacher performance (variable Y) with a coefficient value of $r = 0.581$. This means that there is a positive relationship between the principal's decision making and teacher performance. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the higher the principal's decision-making, the higher the teacher's performance. Thus, the findings of facts and data in the analysis of this study further support the previous findings regarding the existence of a significant relationship between the principal's decision-making and teacher performance.

The Relationship Between Learning Organizations and Teacher Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that the functional relationship between learning organization variables and teacher performance variables is expressed by a simple linear regression equation $= 101.18 + 0.257X_2$, with $F_{count} = 22.775 > F_{table} (0.05) 3.88$ and $F_{table} (0.01) = 6.75$

which means that it is not significant or the regression is linear, meaning that if the learning organization is increased by one unit, the teacher's performance is predicted to increase by 0.257 units with a constant of 101.18. This means that every increase in the score of the learning organization will improve teacher performance. Learning Organizations make a positive contribution to improving teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance is shown by the correlation coefficient r_{y2} of 0.397 with the value of the termination coefficient $R_{y2} = 0.1575$. This means that 15.75% of teacher performance is motivated by learning organizations, while 84.25% is contributed by other variables that have a relationship with teacher performance.

The partial correlation coefficient of the learning organization with the controlling variable for the principal's decision-making is $r_{y2.1} = 0.273$ and the controlling variable for self-efficacy is $r_{y2.3} = 0.279$. From the two partial correlation tests, it can be concluded that the relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance is very significant at the level of $= 0.05$ (1.97) and $= 0.01$ (2.60) with the control variables of teacher empowerment and self-efficacy variables. In other words, the relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance is not significantly influenced by decision-making variables and self-efficacy variables.

From the results of the study, it can be seen that a learning organization is an organization that continuously develops the ability to continuously adapt and change. Thus, doing learning means implementing a strategy of innovation, continuous improvement, commitment to the tasks and goals of the organization. In learning organizations, individuals and their professions are seen as decisive factors to bring about organizational success. Therefore, individuals should not stop learning. He must have a personal vision, be creative, and must be committed to the truth

This research is in line with Michael J. Marquardt (2002: 247), Learning Organization is an organization that learns effectively and collectively and continuously transforms itself into an organization that manages and uses knowledge better empowering people inside and outside the organization to study and work, using technology to maximize learning and production. The learning organization indicators are: a. Dimensions of Learning Level include: 1) Individual learning, 2) Group/team learning and 3) Organizational Learning, b. The dimensions of the type of learning include: 1) Adaptive learning, 2) Anticipatory learning, and 3) Action learning, c. Dimensions of skills learned include: 1) System thinking, 2) Mental models, 3) Personal mastery, and 4) Self-directed learning Dialogue.

The results of previous relevant research were carried out by Yulita Pujilestaria in the Journal of Civics and

Education Studies in his research entitled The Effect of Learning Organizations and School-Based Management on Teacher Performance, shows the high effect of learning organization (X1) on the performance of State Junior High School teachers (Y) with a correlation coefficient of 8.473. This shows that there is a very strong influence of the learning organization variable on the performance of SMP Negeri Tangerang Selatan City teachers. Furthermore, it is explained that there is a significant influence between learning organization on teacher performance in public junior high schools in South Tangerang City Junior High School with the regression equation: $= a + b_2 X_1 = 8,473 + 1,068 X_1$ Where: X1: Learning organization Y: Teacher Performance in State Junior High Schools at SMPN South Tangerang City

The results of the study are based on hypothesis testing which states that there is a functional relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance with significant regression and indicates that every increase in the learning organization score will improve teacher performance.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the higher the learning organization, the higher the teacher's performance. Thus, the findings of facts and data in the analysis of this study further support previous findings regarding the existence of a significant relationship between learning organizations and teacher performance.

The Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Teacher Performance

Based on the results of the research, the functional relationship between the self-efficacy variable and the teacher performance variable was expressed by a simple linear regression equation $= 86.757 + 0.373X_3$, with $F_{count} = 28.902 > F_{table}(0.05) = 3.88$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 6.75$ which means that the significance of the regression is very significant. The functional relationship is linear as evidenced by the linearity test with the value of $F_{count} = -4.33 < F_{table}(0.05) = 1.53$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 1.85$ which means it is not significant or linear regression, in the sense that if self-efficacy is increased by one unit, the teacher's performance is predicted to increase by 0.373 units with a constant of 86.757. This means that every increase in self-efficacy scores will improve teacher performance. Self-efficacy makes a positive contribution to improving teacher performance.

The strength of the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance is shown by the correlation coefficient r_{y3} of 0.441 with a coefficient of determination $R_{y3} = 0.1946$. This means that 19.46% of teacher performance is the result of learning organizations, while 80.54% is contributed by other variables that have a relationship with improving teacher performance.

The partial correlation coefficient of self-efficacy with the principal decision-making variable controller is $r_{y3.1} = 0.326$ and the learning organization variable controller is $r_{y3.2} = 0.319$. From the two partial correlation tests, it can be concluded that the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance is very significant at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, controlling for the decision-making variables of principals and learning organizations. In other words, the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance is not significantly influenced by the decision-making variables of principals and learning organizations.

From the quantitative data from the research, it can be concluded that self-efficacy plays a very important role in everyday life, a person will be able to use his potential optimally if self-efficacy supports it. One aspect of life that is influenced by self-efficacy is achievement. If a teacher has high self-efficacy, the teacher's performance will also increase, because self-efficacy is a person's evaluation of his ability or competence to perform a task, achieve goals, and overcome obstacles.

The results of this study are reinforced by the theory put forward by Gibson et al., (2009:113) that self-efficacy is a belief that we can perform adequately in a particular situation. People's sense of capability influences their perception, motivation, and performance.

Gibson emphasizes that self-efficacy is a belief that can appear adequately in certain situations, where people's abilities affect their perceptions, motivations, and performance. If someone experiences success, his self-efficacy will increase, and high self-efficacy will motivate individuals cognitively to act more diligently and especially if the goals to be achieved are clear.

The results of previous relevant research were carried out by Hani Ratnasari and Nancy Yusnita at JIMFE (Journal of Scientific Management, Faculty of Economics) Vol. 4 No. 1, June 2018, p. 51-66 entitled Analysis of the Relationship of Self-Efficacy with Employee Performance at PT Metraplasa shows that the self-efficacy variable has a significant relationship to employee performance, the correlation between the self-efficacy variable and employee performance shows a value of 0.573. The value of the coefficient of determination shows a percentage of 28.8% where the results show that the contribution of the self-efficacy variable to the employee performance variable is 28.8%. Thus there is a relationship between self-efficacy (X) and employee performance (Y) at PT Metraplasa.

Thus, the findings of facts and data in the analysis of this study further support the previous findings regarding the existence of a strong relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance, both directly and indirectly. The results of hypothesis testing which state that there is a functional relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance with a very significant regression and indicate that any increase in self-efficacy scores will improve teacher performance.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the higher the teacher's self-efficacy, the higher the teacher's performance. Thus, the findings of facts and data in the analysis of this study further support previous findings regarding a significant relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance.

Relationship between Decision Making and Learning Organization together with Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a positive relationship between the decision making of the principal and learning organizations together with teacher performance, this was indicated by the correlation coefficient $r_{y1.2} = 0.386$ which was declared very significant after being tested by the F test. The value of the coefficient of determination between decision making principals and learning organizations $R_{y1.2} = 0.1492$. This means that 14.92% of teacher performance is the contribution of the decision-making relationship between principals and learning organizations together, while 85.08% is contributed by other variables that have to do with teacher performance.

The functional relationship between the principal and organizational decision-making variables together with teacher performance is shown by the multiple linear regression equation $= 70.840 + 0.271X_1 + 0.219X_2$ with a value of $F_{count} = 44.28 > F_{table}(0.05) = 3.04$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 4.70$ which means that the significance of the regression is very significant, this shows that any increase in the decision-making score of the principal and learning organization together will improve teacher performance with a regression coefficient which is stated to be very significant.

The findings in this study that decision-making has a significant impact, which refers to the process of generating and selecting from a set of alternatives to solve a problem, meaning that decision-making is an activity of the principal that must immediately be carried out if the school wants to achieve the desired goals. Decision making in a problem is a solution to the problems it faces, thus decision making is the last action taken by the principal in determining policy. In the decision-making process, there are usually several choices that must be determined which is the best for achieving school goals.

According to Schermerhorn (2009:114) Decision making is a key activity of the principal, the principal plays an important role, especially when the principal carries out the planning function, involving very important and long-term decisions. Decision making describes the process through a series of selected activities as a solution to a particular problem with measurable steps or stages.

According to David A. Garvin (2000:11), a learning organization is an organization that is trained in creating, acquiring, interpreting, transferring and retaining

knowledge and intentionally modifying its organizational behavior to reflect new knowledge and understanding. It was also emphasized that in a learning organization, learning activities occur intentionally and are designed to be carried out within the organization. The learning organization indicators are: a. planning organizational quality development programs, b. modify organizational behavior to create a learning atmosphere and c. transfer knowledge.

A learning organization can be interpreted as an organization that has an integrated system and is always changing, because the individual members of the organization experience a learning process.

Based on the results of the research stated above, it can be concluded that the decision-making of school principals and learning organizations together can make a positive contribution to improving teacher performance.

The Relationship Between Decision Making and Self-Efficacy Together with Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a positive relationship between principal's decision-making and self-efficacy together with teacher performance. This is indicated by the correlation coefficient $r_{y1.3}$ of 0.563 which is stated to be very significant after being tested by the F test. The value of the termination coefficient $R_{y1.3}$ is 0.3173, this means that 31.73% of teacher performance is the result of the work of the principal's decision-making and self-efficacy together, while 68.27% was contributed by other variables that have to do with teacher performance.

The functional relationship between the principal's decision-making variables and self-efficacy together with teacher performance is shown by the multiple linear regression equation = $65.23 + 0.24X_1 + 0.30X_3$ with a value of $F_{count} = 45.00 > F_{table}(0.05) = 3.04$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 4.70$ which means that the significance of the regression is very significant, this shows that any increase in the principal's decision-making score and self-efficacy together will improve teacher performance with a regression coefficient which is stated to be very significant.

Colquitt (2009:244) argues that: Many other companies are focused on promoting knowledge sharing between their employees because learning and decision making are so important in organizations. The quote above can be interpreted that decision making is very important in organizations in promoting and sharing knowledge among employees, in other words that in making a decision to solve a problem that arises from the changes that occur in the organization, good information from the organization is needed. internal and external organizations in order to make the right decisions and quickly. Decision making is a deliberate action, and should not be careless in solving problems faced by schools. This decision-making is borne and decided by

the school principal to produce a decision. A good decision requires complete information about the problem, the core of the problem, problem solving, and the consequences of the decisions taken, then alternative problem decisions are made accompanied by positive and negative consequences, if all of these things can be stated and searched appropriately, the problem it will be easier to solve.

According to Robbins (2008: 436) that self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief that he or she is capable of performing a task. The higher your self-efficacy, the more confidence you have in your ability to succeed. The quote above can be interpreted that self-efficacy is an individual's ability to refer to the individual's belief that he or she is capable of completing a task. The higher the self-efficacy, the more confident in the ability to achieve success. Self-efficacy is self-confidence in one's ability to perform an action required for the desired result. Someone who has high self-efficacy, is able to manage his life to be more successful.

Based on the results of the research presented above, it can be concluded that the principal's decision-making and self-efficacy together can make a positive contribution to improving teacher performance.

Relationship Between Learning Organization and Self-Efficacy Together with Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a positive relationship between learning organizations and self-efficacy together with teacher performance. This is shown by the correlation coefficient $r_{y2.3}$ of 0.409 which is declared very significant after the test with the F test. The value of the coefficient of determination $R_{y2.3}$ is 0.1669, this means that 16.69% of teacher performance is the result of the work of learning organizations and efficacy themselves together, while 83.31% was contributed by other variables that have to do with teacher performance.

The functional relationship between learning organization variables and self-efficacy together with teacher performance is shown by the multiple linear regression equation = $62.97 + 0.233X_2 + 0.334X_3$ with a value of $F_{count} = 50.083 > F_{table}(0.05) = 3.04$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 4.70$ which means that the significance of the regression is very significant, this shows that any increase in the learning organization score and self-efficacy together will improve teacher performance with a regression coefficient which is stated to be very significant.

Daft (2010: 50) states that a learning organization can be defined as one in which everyone is engaged in identifying and solving problems, enabling the organization to continuously experiment, change, and improve, thus increasing its capacity to grow, learn, and achieve its purpose.

A learning organization can be defined as an organization where everyone is involved in identifying and solving problems, thereby enabling the organization to continuously experiment, change, and improve, which ultimately increases its capacity to grow, learn, and achieve its goals.

In learning organizations, individuals and their professions are seen as decisive factors to bring about organizational success. Therefore, individuals should not stop learning. He must have a personal vision, be creative, and must be committed to the truth. He will continue to learn effectively and collectively and continuously transform himself into an organization that better manages and uses knowledge empowering people inside and outside the organization to learn and work, using technology to maximize learning and production.

Wibowo (2015:161) states that self-efficacy is a person's belief that he has the ability to perform a task. In other words, self-efficacy is the ability or ability that a person has, so that if the employee gets the task assigned to him, he will be accepted with pleasure.

Self-efficacy is the ability of the teacher refers to the individual's belief that he is capable of completing a task. The higher the self-efficacy, the more confident in the ability to achieve success. Self-efficacy is self-confidence in one's ability to perform an action required for the desired result.

Schermerhorn (2009:223) states that goals are most likely to lead to higher performance when people have the abilities and the feelings of self-efficacy required to accomplish them. The quote means that goals are most likely to lead to higher performance when people have the abilities and feelings of self-efficacy needed to achieve them. In other words, to achieve maximum performance, one must have high self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is basically the result of a cognitive process in the form of decisions, beliefs, or expectations about the extent to which individuals estimate their abilities to carry out certain tasks or actions needed to achieve the desired results. Based on the results of the research stated above, it can be concluded that learning organizations and self-efficacy together can make a positive contribution to improving teacher performance.

The Relationship Between Principal Decision Making, Learning Organization, and Self-Efficacy Together With Performance

The results showed that there was a positive relationship between the principal's decision-making, learning organizations, and self-efficacy together with teacher performance. This is indicated by the multiple correlation coefficient $r_{y1.2.3} = 0.863$, which is stated to be very significant after being tested by the F test. The coefficient of determination $R_{y1.2.3} = 0.745$, this means that 74.5% of teacher performance is the result of the principal's

decision-making work, learning organization, and self-efficacy together, while 25.5% was contributed by other variables that have to do with teacher performance.

The relationship between the decision-making variables of principals, learning organizations, and self-efficacy together with teacher performance is shown by the multiple linear regression equation $= 89 + -0.089X_1 + 0.118X_2 + 0.377X_3$ with a value of $F_{count} = 16.97 > F_{table}(0.05) = 3.04$ and $F_{table}(0.01) = 4.70$, which means that the significance of the regression is very significant. This shows that each increase in the decision-making score of the principal, learning organization, and self-efficacy together will improve teacher performance with a regression coefficient that is stated to be very significant.

Decision making is the process of identifying problems and opportunities and then solving them. Decision making involves effort, both before and after the actual choice. Decision making is a management activity that must be carried out by the ranks of managers or leaders, in solving organizational problems so that predetermined organizational goals can be realized. In other words, decision making is a process of selecting the best alternative from several alternatives systematically to be followed up (used) as a way of solving problems.

Decision making is one of the important factors for a school principal in carrying out the leadership function. The right decision making by the principal will have a positive impact on teacher performance. Principals not only provide direction and supervision to teachers, but are also required to be able to make the right decisions and communicate important matters in order to create a conducive and dynamic work atmosphere. Such an atmosphere in turn can spur increased performance. Decision making by school principals certainly affects teacher performance.

Learning organizations are organizations that continuously develop the ability to continuously adapt and change. Thus, doing learning means carrying out an innovation strategy, continuous improvement, commitment to the tasks and goals of the organization. A learning organization or learning organization is an organization that continuously strives to improve the abilities of its members. An effective learning organization will give birth to new innovations as a result of learning. Creative teachers are able to utilize existing knowledge to elaborate products and services in managing learning better, and in accordance with the changing environment that is always dynamic. Creative teachers will quickly adapt to changes both in thinking and acting so that there will always be updates in managing learning. On the other hand, teachers who are less creative tend to have difficulty in elaborating changes and new things so that they can hinder the acceleration of continuous innovation. Therefore, schools as learning organizations should optimize teacher empowerment by providing opportunities for self-development which in turn affects

performance improvement.

Self-efficacy is an individual's ability to refer to the individual's belief that he or she is capable of completing a task. The higher the self-efficacy, the more confident in the ability to achieve success. Self-efficacy is self-confidence in one's ability to perform an action required for the desired result. Someone who has high self-efficacy, is able to manage his life to be more successful.

Self-efficacy or self-efficacy is related to a person's belief that he or she is able to perform the assigned task. Teachers who have high self-efficacy are confident of their success and will be more motivated to improve their skills so that it has a significant impact on improving their performance. On the other hand, low self-efficacy makes teachers hesitate to develop their competencies, reduces their participation in groups, thus hindering the contribution of members in innovation activities and new things in their work.

Based on the research stated above, it can be concluded that the decision-making of the principal, learning organization, and self-efficacy together will improve teacher performance. Another finding in this study is that if the simple correlation values are compared, it will be known that the self-efficacy variable has the strongest relationship with teacher performance, followed by the principal's decision-making variable and the learning organization variable, $ry_3 (0.441) > ry_1 (0.412) > ry_2 (0.397)$. The multiple correlation coefficient which has a very strong relationship is the principal's decision-making and self-efficacy variables with teacher performance compared to the double correlation coefficient of learning organizations and teacher efficacy with teacher performance and decision making by principals and learning organizations with teacher performance which has a value of: $ry_1 .3(0.563) > ry_2.3(0.409) > ry_1.2(0.386)$. From the calculation of the coefficient of termination of simple correlation and double correlation of three variables, the values obtained are $Ry_{123} = 74.5\% > Ry_3(19.46\%), Ry_1(16.97\%)$ and $Ry_2(15.75\%)$. The values of the coefficient of determination show that the decision-making variables of the principal, learning organization, and self-efficacy together have a very large influence on teacher performance compared to the influence between each variable, in other words there has been a very strong relationship between principal's decision making with teacher performance, between learning organizations and teacher performance, and between self-efficacy and teacher performance. As previously explained, the results of the analysis of the double correlation of three independent variables with teacher performance, obtained a termination coefficient of $Ry_{1.2.3} = 0.745$. This means that 74.5% of the teacher's performance value is the result of the work of the principal's decision-making factors, learning organizations, and self-efficacy, while 25.5% of the performance value is contributed by

other factors that have a relationship with improving teacher performance..

CONCLUSION

This research uses quantitative research methods and then continues with SITOREM analysis as a follow-up to quantitative research to find out which indicators of each variable must be corrected immediately and which indicators of each variable must be maintained or developed. From the results of the research discussion, which is about the relationship between decision making by principals, learning organizations, and self-efficacy with the performance of State MTs teachers in East Jakarta, the conclusions are as follows:

1. There is a positive and very significant relationship between the principal's decision-making and teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient $ry_1 = 0.412$ and the coefficient of determination $Ry_1 = 0.1697$, meaning that the principal's decision-making contributes to teacher performance by 16.97% .
2. There is a positive and very significant relationship between the learning organization variable and the teacher performance variable. This is indicated by the correlation coefficient $ry_2 = 0.397$ and the coefficient of determination $Ry_2 = 0.1575$ which means that the contribution of learning organizations to teacher performance is 15.75%.
3. There is a positive and very significant relationship between self-efficacy and teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient $ry_3 = 0.441$ and the coefficient of determination $Ry_3 = 0.1946$, meaning that efficacy contributes to teacher performance by 19.46%.
4. There is a positive and very significant relationship between the decision making of principals and learning organizations together with teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient value $ry_{1.2} = 0.386$ and the determination value $Ry_{1.2} = 0.1492$ this means that decision making the decisions of principals and learning organizations together contribute to teacher performance by 14.92%.
5. There is a positive and very significant relationship between decision making and self-efficacy together with teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient $ry_{1.3} = 0.563$ and the determination value $Ry_{1.3} = 0.3173$, this means decision-making and efficacy themselves together contribute to the performance of teachers by 31.73%.
6. There is a positive and very significant relationship between learning organizations and self-efficacy together with teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient $ry_{2.3} = 0.409$ and the determination value $Ry_{2.3} = 0.1669$ which means learning organization and self-efficacy are significantly together contributed to the performance of teachers by 16.69%.

7. There is a positive and very significant relationship between decision making, learning organization, and self-efficacy together with teacher performance as indicated by the correlation coefficient $r_{y1.2.3} = 0.863$ and the determination value $R_{y1.2.3} = 0.745$ which means the principal's decision-making, learning organization, and self-efficacy together contribute to teacher performance by 74.5%.

Based on the results of this study, it can also be seen that the self-efficacy variable has the strongest relationship with teacher performance, followed by the principal's decision-making variable and the learning organization variable with teacher performance, as is known based on the correlation coefficient value of, $r_{y3} (0.441) > r_{y1} (0.412) > r_{y2} (0.397)$. And the self-efficacy variable has a higher relationship value than the principal's decision-making variable and the learning organization variable. individually or jointly, and there is also the role of other variables that have a relationship with improving teacher performance, namely work motivation, compensation, organizational climate, and leadership that are not included in this study. The suggestions in this study can be used as input for school principals, teachers, committees, the Ministry of Religion and related agencies to improve teacher performance in order to improve the quality and performance of schools as part of improving the quality of education. Based on the results of research, discussion, conclusions and implications, then The suggestions put forward for improving teacher performance are in accordance with the order of priority calculations in the SITOREM analysis, namely strengthening self-efficacy, strengthening decision making, and strengthening learning organizations.

1) Strengthening Self-Efficacy for Teachers to improve indicators; Develop abilities and achievements, have an optimistic view in doing assignments, through the form of Training or Workshop activities that are able to foster confidence and confidence in teachers in managing learning according to their abilities and competencies

2) Strengthening Decision Making by improving weak indicators, namely; Identify and define problems through the form of a 'Problem Solving and Decision Making Workshop' for school principals. With this activity, the principal is expected to be able to make quality decisions and be able to deal with problems quickly and effectively.

3) Strengthening Learning Organizations by improving indicators; Mutual trust in each other and able to solve common problems, Able to formulate organizational values in order to solve organizational problems, through empowerment of Madrasah Working Groups (KKM), Empowerment of Subject Teacher Consultations

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